

Industry 4.0 Conference: The relationship of privacy and trust within the IoT Technology Acceptance Model

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ABSTRACT

IoT solutions enable service providers to collect personal data on their customers to increase the functionality of the devices and to create value-added services. In this study the user acceptance of IoT solutions is explained with IoT-TAM model. The current model contains seven variables including trust. Trust concerns the quality of the device which guarantees the accuracy of the data. Privacy is not mentioned in the current model, but could have an influence on the user acceptance. Privacy concerns to what extent, when and how the data is communicated to others. This resulted in the following research question: ‘To what extent are privacy and trust related, and to what extent is privacy related to the integrated IoT-TAM model to make it applicable for IoT solutions?’. Literature research shows the relationship between privacy, trust, and the IoT-TAM model, but the survey results show contradictions. Therefore, this relationship could not be established.

KEYWORDS

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Internet-of-Things (IoT), Privacy, Trust, Internet-of-Things-Technology Acceptance model (IoT-TAM model).

INTRODUCTION

Internet-of-Things (IoT) allows autonomous and secure connections to exchange data between devices and applications with unique identifiers without human interaction (Khan, R. et al. 2012). This technology is becoming a more relevant topic for enterprises and society. For example, enterprises are using track and trace devices to secure the location of products and valuables. Insurance companies are using IoT technologies to measure factors which have an influence on the risk of the users to determine the premium. The Apple watch is an example of an IoT technology which is used by consumers. The consumers use their Apple watch for payments, tracking activities, tracking location and navigation.

IoT solutions enable service providers to collect personal data on their customers to increase the functionality of the devices or value-added

services could be created. Using IoT solutions to collect personal data of their customers requires acceptance of the users. Therefore, social acceptance of using Internet-of-Things is important for the implementation of an IoT solution and final adoption among users. However, collecting personal data can result in privacy and ethical risks. In this paper the user acceptance of IoT solutions of services providers will be researched.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

IoT is a new technology which enables items to exchange information about themselves and their surroundings (Bandyopadhyay, D., & Sen, J. 2011). IoT links physical activities to the virtual world through autonomous and secure connections. (Khan, R., Khan, S. U., Zaheer, R., & Khan, S. 2012, December). It could lead to innovative services an increase in productivity and an increase in efficiency (Bandyopadhyay, D., & Sen, J. 2011).

IoT-TAM model is a generalized model for predicting the user acceptance towards IoT technologies. This model contains several variables; perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, trust, social influence, perceived enjoyment, perceived behavioural control (Lingling, 2014).

Trust is defined as which connects the intelligent objects to the technological ecosystems (Riahi, A., Challal, Y., Natalizio, E., Chtourou, Z., & Bouabdallah, A. 2013). The importance of trust is widely acknowledged, because it improves the relationships in various settings (McKnight, D. H., & Chervany, N. L. 1996). Trust could be categorized in four dimensions; device trust, processing trust, connecting trust and system trust (Daubert, J., et al. 2015, June).

The current IoT-TAM model does not contain the variable privacy. Privacy is the ability of individuals to determine to what extent, when and how their information is communicated to others (Westin, A. F. 1968). The importance of privacy lies in the risk of misusing personal data, which makes people vulnerable (Dinev, T., & Hart, P. 2006). Privacy could be categorized along the following dimensions; identity privacy, location privacy, footprint privacy and query privacy (Daubert, J., Wiesmaier, A., & Kikiras, P. 2015, June).

According to Daubert (2015) trust and privacy differ from each other. Trust concerns the quality of the device which guarantees the accuracy of the data. Privacy concerns to what extent, when and how their data is communicated to others (Daubert, J, et al., 2015). Literature shows that one of the most prominent causes for consumer's rejection of smart meter is their concerns of violation of privacy (Al Abdulkarim, L., Lukszo, Z., & Fens, T. 2012). In addition, Gao (2014) defined systems which obtain highly valuable data to function are more likely to be rejected than systems which contain less valuable data (Gao, L., & Bai, X. 2014).

This paper investigates the relationship between privacy, trust and the IoT-TAM model. Besides that, there is investigated to what extent privacy and trust are influencing the behavioural intention to use. This results in a study on how privacy affects the IoT-TAM model for using IoT solutions.

RESEARCH QUESTION

The research question for this study states as follows: 'To what extent are privacy and trust related, and to what extent is privacy related to the integrated IoT-TAM model to make it applicable for IoT solutions?' To be able to answer the research question, it is divided in theoretical and practical sub-questions. The theoretic sub-questions focus on context and variable elaboration, creating an unambiguous understanding among the readers.

Theoretical sub-questions:

1. What is IoT?
2. What is trust?
3. What is privacy?
4. What is the IoT-TAM model?
5. How are privacy and trust related?

Practical sub-questions:

6. To what extent do privacy and trust influence the behavioural intention to use?
7. To what extent influences a model expansion the other variables of the IoT-TAM model and their relation to the behavioural intention to use?
8. How does privacy affect the IoT-TAM model for using IoT solutions?

RELEVANCE

Managerial relevance

Our findings will be of interest to several service providers in the Netherlands. By considering new IoT solutions as part of their products, deliberate decisions need to be made. To support organizations by adopting the new solution among their customers, the revised IoT-TAM model will

give a complete overview which requirements need to be met. The revised IoT-TAM model will contribute to a higher customer acceptance on newly introduced IoT solutions, enabling the service providing companies to obtain customer insights.

Academic relevance

In this research, there is investigated which variables are relevant for adopting new IoT solutions among consumers. The literature of Lingling (2014) is stated to further investigate the integrated TAM model of this study. There seems to be a gap between the current model and the literature research. The research findings implied the relation privacy and social acceptance of consumers, on newly introduced IoT solutions. This knowledge gap will be filled by further investigating this relation. Likely, resulting in a more generalizable model for adopting newly introduced IoT solutions, applicable to different industries.

THEORY

TAM Model

The TAM model is a generalized model for technology acceptance, this was the principle for this paper. The integrated model, developed by Lingling (2014), is a high-quality proven paper which is cited many times by multiple scientific researches.

User acceptance is defined as the demonstrable willingness within a user group to employ information technology for the tasks it is designed to support (Dillon and Morris, 1996). Without acceptance, users will probably exhibit performance problems and dissatisfaction, resulting in an inefficient way of adapting to the new technology. Therefore, user acceptance can be seen as a determining variable for the success or failure of any information system project (Lingling, 2014). IoT technology has an increasing impact on our daily lives, research into factors determining consumers' acceptance of IoT technology is needed. The TAM model is defined as a generalized model for predicting information system acceptance and diagnosing design problems before users having experience with a system (Lingling, 2014). As the TAM model focuses on new technologies, it can be further developed for an application in IoT solutions. The integrated model shown in figure 1, is an application from IoT perspectives on the TAM model. The model aims at variables which influence users' acceptance of IoT technologies in an integrated manner.

The integrated model, which is an extension from the TAM Model by involving IoT acceptance to the model, added several new variables. In short, the model focuses on:

- Perceived usefulness, innovations providing a unique advantage compared to existing solutions (Rogers, 1995).
- Perceived ease of use, users perceived pursued efforts when using IoT technologies. Perceived ease of use has a positive impact on the perceived usefulness of IoT technologies (Lingling, 2014).
- Trust, the perceived risk associated with a product or service (Kim and Lennon, 2013). Trust has a positive effect on the perceived usefulness of IoT technologies.
- Social influence, a users' perception of whether other important people perceived they should engage in the behaviour (Lingling, 2014).
- Perceived enjoyment, the extent to which the activity of adopting IoT technologies is perceived to be enjoyable, apart from any performance consequences that may be anticipated (Deci, 1971).
- Perceived behavioural control, describes users' perception if they have the necessary resources, capability, and a sense of control in successfully performing the behaviour. Users need to possess the basic skills to use IoT systems/devices (Lingling, 2014).

Perceived ease of use and trust are both found
 Figure 1 Integrated model by TAM application

to affect the perceived usefulness. Although trust has no direct effect on the behavioural intention (insignificant), its indirect effect on the usage intention through perceived usefulness should not be ignored (Lingling, 2014). These three variables are the technology factors in the model. Perceived enjoyment and perceived behavioural control are two individual user characteristics. Social influence is the only social context factor in the model which may be debatable, since privacy is not mentioned in the model. In the case of user acceptance, privacy as a social context factor must be mentioned, since

consumers are worried about the way personal information is managed (Wu, K. W., Huang, S. Y., Yen, D. C., & Popova, I. 2012). Adding privacy to the model seems like a legit reason to expand the model and further research the relations.

IoT

The term IoT is used as an umbrella keyword for various aspects which are relating to the internet and the web into the physical realm. These devices are embedded with sensing, actuation and/or identification capabilities (Miorandi, D., Sicari, S., De Pellegrini, F., & Chlamtac, I. 2012). IoT allows autonomous and secure connections to exchange data between real world devices and applications. IoT links physical activities to the virtual world (Khan, R. et al. 2012). These items could exchange information about themselves and their surroundings. This could lead to innovative services and an increase in productivity and an increase in efficiency (Bandyopadhyay, D., & Sen, J. 2011). This will give rise to new opportunities for the Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) sector, paving the way to new services and applications able to leverage the interconnection of physical and virtual realms (Miorandi, D., et al. 2012).

Privacy

Privacy is highly cherished value and according to the theory of Maslow it is one of the basic needs of human beings (Arlow, J. A. 1955). The importance of privacy lies in the risk of misusing personal data, which makes people vulnerable (Dinev, T., & Hart, P. 2006). As earlier mentioned, privacy is the ability of individuals to determine to what extent, when and how their information is communicated to others (Westin, A. F. 1968). In this conceptualization, privacy is a right of people to control their data and not having undocumented personal information possessed by others.

IoT constantly measures, transfers and shares personal data using the internet. When devices are constantly connected to the internet with no borders or regulated restrictions, privacy becomes a major concern for consumers in using IoT services (Wu, K. W., Huang, S. Y., Yen, D. C., & Popova, I. 2012). The data exchange of IoT services remains a major challenge, because of the consequences of leaking sensitive data. Privacy is categorized along four dimensions. (1. Identity privacy: refers to the need to secure data which refers to the identity of a person like name, address, age. (2. Location privacy: refers to data that follows and registers the location of the object that is using the IoT devices like google maps. (3. Footprint privacy: is unintentionally leaked personal information like police records or medical records. (4. Query Privacy: privacy refers to the need of privacy regarding answering a query like Siri on an iPhone (Daubert, J., et al. 2015, June).

From these four dimensions, privacy could be defined identifiable information which is related to a person or object.

Trust

Scholars and practitioners widely acknowledge the importance of trust, because it is the key to positive interpersonal relationships in various settings and it is centralised how we interact (McKnight, D. H., & Chervany, N. L. 1996). As earlier mentioned, trust is defined as ‘the tension that ties the intelligent object with the technological ecosystem’ (Riahi, A., et al. 2013). In this conceptualization, trust represents the level of confidence that the environment can grant to the intelligent object.

The IoT environment uses smart objects which are human carried or human-related devices containing personal information. The level of trust in these devices, systems and services becomes a fundamental issue, because of the ability to keep this sensitive data safe (Wu, K. W., Huang, S. Y., Yen, D. C., & Popova, I. 2012). The level of trust is determined by the conception that the devices and systems are technical capable of storing and processing the data. Trust is divided into four dimensions (1. Device trust: refers to the need of using reliable devices. (2. Processing trust: refers to the need for working with correct and meaningful data. (3. Connection trust: refers to the requirement to exchange the right data with the right service providers. (4. Systems trust refers to the need of working with the overall systems (Daubert, J., et al. 2015, June). From these four dimensions, trust is the level of confidence in the IoT solution to process and store the data correct and safe.

Relation trust and privacy

As earlier mentioned, privacy is the risk of misusing personal data which makes people vulnerable and mainly focuses on the sensitiveness of the data and the type of data which is being used (Dinev, T., & Hart, P. 2006). Trust represent the level of confidence that people can grant to an intelligent object and mainly focuses on the technologies which are used to gather and process that data about objects or people (Riahi, A., et al. 2013). Privacy and trust have an influence on each other. When the level of trust in the IoT solution is high it is more likely to share privacy related data with an IoT solution. This relation follows the insight that a higher need for trust is caused by a higher need of privacy (Gao, L., Bai, X. 2014).

CONCEPTUAL MODEL

The conceptual model shown in figure 2 describes the expected relationship between the variables. The model consists of a dependent variable, six independent variables and a partial mediator. The independent variable trust in this

model has a relationship on the dependent variable through the partial mediator. The integrated model consists of eight variables. All the variables will be researched, the main focus will be on the variables: trust, privacy and behavioural intention to use, since an undiscovered relation is expected.

Hypotheses

The conceptual model leads to the following hypotheses:

H1: Trust has an indirect relation on the behavioural intention to use.

H2: Privacy has a direct relation on the behavioural intention to use.

H3: Trust has a direct relation on privacy

H4-H9: variable has a direct relation on behavioural intention to use.

Figure 2 Conceptual model

H1 - The relation of trust on the behaviour intention to use

Trust is an important variable in the IoT-TAM model defined as ‘the perceived risk associated with a product or service’ (Kim and Lennon, 2013). Trust concerns the capabilities of the device for protecting and guaranteeing the accuracy and safety of data transmission (Riahi, A., Challal, et al. 2013). The IoT-TAM model uses trust as variable which contains the level of trust in the technical competences of the technologies.

H2 - The relation of privacy on the behaviour intention to use

Collecting personal data by a service provider through an IoT solution, can lead to privacy risks. When a consumer gives their data, they might not be fully aware of who has access to their data. This can lead to privacy concerns of the consumers and so the

behaviour intention to use an IoT solution.

One of the most prominent causes for consumer's rejection of IoT solutions is due to their concern of violation of private information (privacy) maintained by the ICT infrastructure (Al Abdulkarim., et al. 2012). Therefore, the level of privacy will influence the choice to use the technology.

H3 - The relation of trust on privacy

The level of privacy is expected to have no influence on the IoT technology if the consumer trusts the capabilities of the provider. Trust is mainly driven by the confidence customers have in IoT solutions. Since privacy mainly focuses on the willingness of providing information to an organization. Organizational trust by the customer increases the willingness to provide data for commercial perspectives. IoT solutions which gather sensitive consumer data have a relationship to privacy.

H4 - The other variables that have a direct relation on the behavioural intention to use

In the previous research of Lingling (2014), the other variables from the TAM model- related to the behavioural intention to use conclude a direct relation (Lingling, 2014). In this research, these variables will not be affected and there will be assumed that the direct relationships remain the same. Based on the theoretical review, we expect the variation of the other variables except for trust, are influenced minimally by extending the IoT-TAM model with the variable privacy.

RESEARCH DESIGN

Method

Secondary data is analysed to gather qualitative data about IoT, TAM model, trust and privacy. This results in a higher level of knowledge about the researched subject. Primary data is needed, because the relation of privacy and trust concerning the IoT-TAM model is not stated in existing literature (Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. 2016). To test the general usefulness of the IoT-TAM model data is needed from the total population. Survey research will describe the characteristics of a large population, no other research technique can provide a broader view than survey research (Krosnick, J. A., 1999).

The population of this study consists of all the inhabitants from the Netherlands. The sampling frame consists of adults who are 18 years or older. Convenience sampling is used in this study, because the amount of time a budget was restricted. The gender, age, education-level of each respondent needs to be filled as general information. If people

are not belonging to the population, they will be removed from the sample. The sampling size needs to be at least 70 respondents, because the sample size must be ten times larger than the number of parameters (7 parameters). An electronic survey will be shared so each person could administer. Assuming a response rate of 10% at least 700 people needs to be approached (Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. 2016).

Measurement Procedure

Close ended question will be asked in the survey, because it will help to make quick decision and are easy to analyse (Krosnick, J. A., 1999). The survey starts with comforting the respondent by stating that all the answers are anonymous and will be processed carefully. The first questions state general information (gender, study, province). The results of these questions could be used to test if the sample is reliable for the whole population of the Netherlands. Secondly follows a short introduction about IoT and a question to test their basic knowledge.

The measurements for the survey are shown in figure 3. The questions from the previous study are used to measure the existing variables of the model. The variables trust and privacy are measured with new questions, based on the literature review. (Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. 2016).

The question concerning the IoT-TAM model are tested with a Likert scale. This is a technique which gives insights in the rating of positive and negative feelings toward variables. Non-comparative scale is used, because benchmarking is needed to make it possible to generalize the renewed IoT-TAM model. Otherwise only a specific object or situation could be described with the model (Boone, H. N., & Boone, D. A. 2012).

Interpreting data

Per variable the results of the questions are clustered to calculate the mean result. Each of the respondents gave a score using the Likert scale. The results will be interpreted and analysed by using an ANOVA table. In this table the determination coefficient (R^2) will explain the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable. The adjusted coefficient of determination (R^2_{adj}) can be used to obtain the difference between the models. Also, the direction coefficients ($B_0, B_1, B_2, \dots, B_7$) and the significance of each variable could be determined to interpret the usefulness of the model (Nieuwenhuis, G. 2009). At last, the following formula will be used to compare the complete IoT-TAM model including the variable privacy with the reduced model without the variable privacy:

$$F = \frac{(Rc^2 - Rr^2) / (k - g)}{(1 - Rc^2) / (n - (k + 1))}$$

Construct name:	Measurement:	Source:
General	close-ended questions; age, gender, education level, residence province, and 'do you know what IoT solutions are?	Own development
Perceived usefulness	Five point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree; 2=disagree; 3=neutral; 4=agree; 5=strongly agree). - IoT solutions provide a unique advantage compared to existing solutions - Using IoT solutions would increase the quality or output of my life - I would find using new IoT solutions disadvantageous until the value is widely proven.	(Lingling, 2014).
Perceived ease of use	Five point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree; 2=disagree; 3=neutral; 4=agree; 5=strongly agree). - I would experience efforts when using the IoT solutions. - Learning how to use the IoT solutions seems easy for me. - I think using IoT solutions is vague and unclear.	(Lingling, 2014).
Trust	Five point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree; 2=disagree; 3=neutral; 4=agree; 5=strongly agree). - I trust that the IoT devices provide reliable information - I trust that the IoT devices gather correct and meaningful data - I do not trust the capability of the devices to gather, process and share my data.	(Daubert, J., Wiesmaier, A., Kikiras, P. 2015). (Wu, K. W., Huang, S. Y., Yen, D. C.; Popova, I. 2012).
Privacy	Five point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree; 2=disagree; 3=neutral; 4=agree; 5=strongly agree). I am willing to provide private data in return for the IoT solutions. - I will only provide private data to a company when being sure of the trustworthiness of their services. - I would not use the IoT solution, when private data is gathered by the IoT solution. - I would not like to share personal information for IoT solutions	(Daubert, J., Wiesmaier, A., Kikiras, P. 2015). (Wu, K. W., Huang, S. Y., Yen, D. C.; Popova, I. 2012).
Social influence	Five point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree; 2=disagree; 3=neutral; 4=agree; 5=strongly agree). - I would use the IoT solution, when people who are important to me would recommend using it. - I would use the IoT solution, when people who are important to me would find using IoT beneficial. - I would not use the IoT solutions when people who are important would find using IoT a good idea	(Lingling, 2014).
Perceived enjoyment	Five point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree; 2=disagree; 3=neutral; 4=agree; 5=strongly agree). - I have fun with using IoT solutions - Using IoT solutions is pleasurable - I do not enjoy using IoT solutions	(Lingling, 2014).
Perceived behavioural control	Five point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree; 2=disagree; 3=neutral; 4=agree; 5=strongly agree). - Using IoT solution is entirely within my control - I have the resources, knowledge and ability to use IoT solutions - I am not skillfully able to use IoT solutions	(Lingling, 2014).
Behavioural intention to use	Five point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree; 2=disagree; 3=neutral; 4=agree; 5=strongly agree). - I am willing to use the IoT solution in the near future. - I would recommend using IoT to others. - I will not give IoT a chance, since there are too many disadvantages.	(Lingling, 2014).
Control	open-ended question: are there any missing criteria to evaluate the willingness to use IoT solutions?	Own development

Figure 3 (Survey measurements)

Reliability

The measurement reliability can be controlled by using Cronbach’s alpha. This technique is used when multiple questions are measuring one item. The value of Cronbach’s alpha must be at least 0.7, to consider it as acceptable (Tavakol, M., & Dennick, R. 2011). The paper of Lingling (2014) is considered as a high-quality article. For that reason, the survey questions which are stated in the article are used to improve the reliability of the research. The influence of privacy and trust could be isolated, because the questions are not influencing each other (Lingling, 2014).

Literature review is used to determine measurement for privacy and trust. This is accomplished by using high-quality articles to increase the reliability of the measurements (Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. 2016).

Validity

Multi-items measurements are used to test the conceptual overlap between the different variables. Single items never capture the context completely (Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. 2016). The questions are simply asked without any bias and all contain the same Likert scale (1 to 5) (Boone, H. N., & Boone, D. A. 2012). The internal validity could be affected by using survey research, because the research subjects are aware that they are part of a scientific study. The respondents might give socially desirable answers which will not correspond with their real actions. The external validity could be affected, because the used variables of the TAM model are studied in China. The influence or interpretation of variables could be contrasting in different countries (Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. 2016).

RESULTS

Convenience sampling was used to draw a sample from the population. The survey was filled in by 53 respondents. Data cleaning is used to examine the sample, so all the elements will belong to the population. After this process 50 respondents were left. Table 1 shows the Cronbach’s Alpha for each variable which is included in the research design (Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. 2016).

Table 2 Cronbach's Alpha

Variable:	Cronbach's Alpha:
Perceived usefulness	0,4820
Perceived ease of use	0,4260
Trust	0,8036
Privacy	0,8088
Social Influence	0,6767
Perceived enjoyment	0,6902
Perceived behavioural control	0,6498
Behavioural intention to use	0,6613

Table 2 shows the coefficient of the slope and the significance of the variables for the reduced and the complete model. The reduced model consists of the original variables which were examined in the IoT-TAM model. The complete model consists of all the variables which were examined for the extended IoT-TAM model.

Table 3 Slope and significance

Variable:	Reduced model:	Significance:	Complete model:	Significance:
Constant	-0,4014	0,3812	-0,0661	0,8826
Perceived usefulness	0,2976	0,0293	0,2583	0,0449
Perceived ease of use	0,3399	0,0232	0,2662	0,0617
Trust	0,2442	0,0250	0,1582	0,1364
Privacy	N/A	N/A	0,2332	0,0131
Social Influence	0,1167	0,2263	0,0518	0,5797
Perceived enjoyment	0,0692	0,6006	0,0466	0,7080
Perceived behavioural control	0,0994	0,4148	0,1058	0,3564

Table 3 shows the following coefficients; R Square, Adjusted R Square, F-Ratio, and significance of F-Ratio. These are examined for the reduced and the complete model. To compare the complete model with the reduced model a F-test is used. The operationalized formula is:

$$\frac{(0,7150 - 0,6695) / (7 - 6)}{(1 - 0,7150) / (50 - (7 + 1))} = 6,7053.$$

Table 1 coefficients of Complete and reduced model

Coefficients:	Reduced model:	Complete model:
R Square	0,6695	0,7150
Adjusted R Square	0,6233	0,6675
F-Ratio	14,5146	15,0557
Significance F-ratio	0,0000	0,0000

DISCUSSION

To gather our data, convenience sampling is used which is a cheap, easy and fast way to get an indication of the user acceptance towards IoT technologies. A main disadvantage of convenience sampling is the low generalizability. The total amount of response was 50 after data cleaning. The low sample size results in a high standard error, which causes variation around the sample mean. The golden standard requires a sample between 75 and 500 respondents for a large enough sample size. In addition to that the requirement of at least 10 respondents per parameters has not been met. The combination of not approving the golden rule and convenience sampling, lacks the generalizability of this research.

The Cronbach’s Alpha measures the reliability from the different elements within the same variable. A high Cronbach’s Alpha is necessary to represent the validity of a variable. A Cronbach’s Alpha of at least 0.70 is acceptable. Therefore, the items which measures the most relevant variables in our research (trust and privacy), seem to be reliable. The way trust and privacy in the questionnaire were assessed is consistent.

However, the other variables are not meeting the acceptance level. The questions which are measuring these items require concrete description to improve the reliability of the outcomes of the questionnaire.

The results of the survey show that privacy has a negative influence on the significance of the other variables. The significance of Perceived behavioural control is the only variable, which has increased, by 5,84 percent. The significance of the six other variables is on average decreased by 18,80 percent.

On the other hand, the R Square of the reduced model states that 66,95 percent of the model is explained by the coefficients of the slope. When the complete model is used the R Square states that 71,50 percent of the model is explained by the coefficients of the slope. There can be concluded that the Adjusted R Squares increased with 4,42 percent, which means that the complete model is more accurate than the reduced model.

From the operationalized formula to compare the complete model with the reduced model there can be concluded that the model has been improved with a confidence of 98 percent. The model is improved if the operationalized formula is higher than $F_{0,02;1;42} = 5,8382$, since the value is 6,7052 there can be concluded that the model is improved.

CONCLUSION

The relationship between trust and privacy and the acceptance of an IoT technology is examined in this research. The IoT-TAM model is used to determine the social acceptance of IoT technology. Literature review has shown that trust and privacy have an influence on the social acceptance of the model. Therefore, it is concluded that there is a relation between privacy and trust toward the behavioural intention to use.

The results of the survey research show contradictions, for that reason this study cannot conclude that privacy is improving or deteriorating the IoT-TAM model. To prove this relation future research is needed.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This research lacks certain limitations. First, the study focuses only on the Dutch population. For that reason, the model needs to be proved in other countries, before it could be obtained.

Second, to generalize the variables of the model specific cases need to be studied to determine if the results are holding in specific cases.

third, the results of the survey do not provide sufficient information to conclude that privacy is significantly improving or impairing the IoT-TAM

model. Certain techniques need to be used to improve the reliability of the research. The Cronbach's Alpha of almost every variable indicates that the questions are not measuring the same aspects. The questions which are measuring the variables need to be adjusted, so the Cronbach's Alpha is improving. In addition to that more respondents are needed to reduce the standard error of the variables. Lastly, most of the respondents were living in two provinces. Besides that, most of the respondents are well educated. None of the respondents were 30 to 55 years old. As a result, the sample does not represent the population. To gather more reliable results a different sampling technique needs to be used.

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